

A new subspecies of *Salamandra algira* Bedriaga, 1883 from northern Morocco

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INTRODUCTION

The genus *Salamandra* is widespread throughout Europe, North Africa and the Middle East (JOGER & STEINFARTZ, 1994). It contains six species of which only one, *Salamandra algira*, is hitherto recognised from North Africa (see BONS, 1972; STEINFARTZ et al., 2000), where it inhabits Morocco and Algeria (BONS & GENIEZ, 1996; SCHLEICH et al., 1996). Its occurrence in Tunisia (SALVADOR, 1996) is questionable.

The species status of *Salamandra algira* was initially proposed by BONS (1972) based on morphology and anecdotal observations on breeding behaviour. It was first supported by GASSER (1978) who showed that the Algerian *S. algira* (from Chrea and Kabylia) possess an exclusive set of alleles not found in any other *Salamandra* species or subspecies. Recent genetic analyses support these findings (JOGER & STEINFARTZ 1994, VEITH, 1994; STEINFARTZ et al., 2000). The latter estimate that *S. algira* separated about 8 million years ago from the European *Salamandra*. They also note that the genetic differences between *S. algira* from Chefchauen, Morocco and *S. algira* from Mount (= Jabal) Edough, Algeria indicate that a separation might have taken place about 6-7 million years ago.

Figure 1. Terra typica of *Salamandra algira* ssp.: Jabal Musa and Jabal el Fahies as seen from the Strait of Gibraltar.

As *S. algira* has no holotype, a neotype was designated by EISELT (1958): NHMW 9251, from Algeria with terra typica "Mont Edough bei Bna" [Mt. Edough near Bna]. STEINFARTZ et al. (2000) use *S. algira* ssp. for the Moroccan specimen. We use this same split and refer to the Moroccan specimen as *S. algira* ssp.

Because little is known about this species, we started our research on *S. algira* in 1995. Since then several field trips to North Africa, chiefly to north of Morocco (figs. 1,2,3) but also to Tunisia, have been made to collect data on biology, ecology, distribution and regional variations. Here we describe a new subspecies from northwest Morocco and Ceuta (Spain) on the basis of morphological, genetic and biological differences.

Figure 2. Terra typica of *Salamandra algira* ssp. n.: eastern slopes of Jabal el Fahies.

Figure 3. Habitat of *Salamandra algira* ssp. n.: karst formations at Jabal Bugmil approximately two km north of Taleta Tagramt.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Morphological and ecological data

Morphological and ecological information on this species was gathered from the literature, museum specimens, fieldtrips and from observations on animals in captivity. In total 24 field trips were made mainly in the humid season, viz. autumn, winter and early spring (October-March).

Our investigations on the distribution of this species focused on finding aquatic larvae during the humid season, which is the easiest way to tell if the species is present. Night excursions were also made at places that seemed suitable during the daytime. Suitability of habitats was predicted through experience with South Iberian *Salamandra salamandra* subspecies. Terrarium observations (since December 1997) were used to study behaviour, development of colour patterns and reproductive mode.

Museum specimens were studied from the British Museum of Natural History, London, U.K. (BMNH); Estación Biológica Doñana, Seville, Spain (EBD); Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, Berkeley, U.S.A. (MZV); Herpetological collection of the Department of Biology of the University of Tetuan, Morocco (DBT); Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Austria (NHMW);

Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt, Germany (SMF); Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain (MNCN), and the Zoölogisch Museum Amsterdam, The Netherlands (ZMA). Specimens from the following collections were studied for this paper:

- BMNH 1889.3.12.9-16, Benider Mountains near Tangier, Morocco (subadults and juveniles), collector H. Vaucher.
- BMNH 1889.12.7.6-7, Bona (= Annaba), Algeria (adult and subadult), collector Hagenmüller.
- BMNH 1920.1.20.1194, Mount (= Jabal) Edough , Algeria (four adults), collector Hagenmüller (Lataste Collection).
- BMNH 1920.1.20.3349, Mount Edough near Bona, Algeria (juvenile), collector L. Bedel (Lataste Collection).
- EBD 29787, Chefchauen (= Xauen), Aïn Tisimilan, Morocco (adult), collector D. Donaire Barroso.
- MVZ 177904, 18.8 km S.E. of Chefchauen, Morocco (subadult), collector S. Busack.
- MNCN 904-907 Imasinen, Beni Seddat, Morocco (four subadults), collector F. Galán.
- SMF 146-147: Benider Mountains near Tangier, Morocco (two juveniles), collector H. Vaucher, donated by G. A. Boulenger in 1889.
- SMF 149-151, Sidi Aissa, near Bona, Algeria (3 adults), donated by A. Knoblauch.

For the description and determination of a new form of *Salamandra algira* specimens have been deposited in the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (MNCN), Madrid, Spain; Zoologisches Forschungsinstitut und Museum Alexander Koenig (ZFMK), Bonn, Germany, and the Zoölogisch Museum Amsterdam (ZMA), The Netherlands.

Live salamanders were studied in the field from the following localities (names are derived from Spanish-Arabic transliteration as most of the cartography used is of Spanish origin):

- Taleta Tagramt, Jabal Musa, Jabal el Fahies, and the Spanish autonomous city of Ceuta. All of these localities are situated north of Tetuan.
- Aïn Lahassen and Cudia Adru, both of which are situated west of Tetuan.
- Chefchauen and Akshur near Talembot, both of which are situated south of Tetuan in the Rif Mountains.
- East of Bab Berret and Jabal Aaloul (Mounts of Ketama), both of which are situated in the central Rif Mountains.
- Ras el Ma of Oued Taza, which is south of Taza in the Middle Atlas.
- Seraidi, Mount Edough, (near Annaba), Algeria (captive specimen).

Body measurements were taken from live animals and museum specimens with a dial calliper and noted to the nearest 0.1 mm. Coloration and colour pattern were photographically documented.

Molecular and phylogenetic analysis

Salvador Carranza (Dept. Zoology, Natural History Museum, London) carried out all of the molecular and phylogenetic analyses. A total of ten specimens of the family Salamandridae were used in this study (see Table I). The sample included the following specimens: 4 *Salamandra algira* ssp. (from 4 different localities in northern Morocco), one *Salamandra atra*, one *Salamandra salamandra morenica*, one *Salamandra salamandra longirostris*, and two *Mertensiella caucasica*. The latter two specimens were used as outgroups. DNA extraction and amplification were carried out using methods described by CARRANZA et al. (2000, 2001). Primers employed in both amplification and sequencing were Salvi1 (5'- TTC AAC TAC AAA AAC CTA ATG ACC C -3') and cytochrome *b*2 (KOCHER et al., 1989).

No gaps had to be included for the cytochrome *b* (cytb) alignment and no stop codons were observed when the sequences were translated as amino acids using the vertebrate mitochondrial code. This suggests that all the cytb sequences analysed were functional. In total, 372 bp of the cytb were included in the phylogenetic analyses. Two methods of phylogenetic analysis were employed and their results compared. These were maximum-likelihood (ML), and maximum-parsimony (MP). Modeltest (POSADA & CRANDALL, 1998) was used to select the most appropriate model of sequence evolution for the ML analysis

under the Akaike Information Criterion. This was the Transversion Model (TVM) of sequence evolution of RODRIGUEZ et al. (1990), taking into account the shape of the Gamma distribution (G). Both ML and MP analyses were performed in PAUP* 4.0b10 (SWOFFORD, 2002) and included heuristic searches involving tree bisection and reconnection (TBR) branch swapping with 100 random stepwise additions of taxa. In the MP analyses, transversions were given the same weight as transitions. Robustness of the ML and MP results was assessed by bootstrap analysis (FELSENSTEIN, 1985) involving 1000 pseudo replications.

We have used Kimura 2-parameters genetic distances to make the data comparable to the majority of studies already published.

RESULTS

Ecology

We have compared two populations of *Salamandra algira* spp. from the most northern part of their distribution in Morocco (from Jabal Musa and Taleta Tagramt) with other populations of *Salamandra algira* spp. The first population was already known for its viviparous mode of reproduction (DONAIRE BARROSO & BOGAERTS, 2001; DONAIRE BARROSO et al., 2001). All other populations known from Morocco and Algeria are ovoviviparous (SCHLEICH et al, 1996; BONIS & GENIEZ, 1996; pers. obs.). We have observed five births of completely metamorphosed young. The first birth episode was spread between January and March 1999 in which one female produced eleven young (DONAIRE BARROSO & BOGAERTS, 2001). The second was in November 1999 when a female produced 17 young (DONAIRE BARROSO et al., 2001). However, sometimes aquatic larvae near metamorphosis are found early in the rainy season in the wild in Jabal Musa (MARTÍNEZ-MEDINA, 2001) and in captivity. In captivity, aquatic larvae have been found twice (once in 2001 and once in 2003). In one case, the aquatic larvae remained aquatic for about four weeks and they metamorphosed at a length of 41-47 mm (n = 2). In the other case they were only aquatic for a week or less, and metamorphosed at a mean length of 31.1 mm (n=14). Viviparous neonates have a mean length of 33.9 mm (n=11) (DONAIRE BARROSO & BOGAERTS, (2001).

Morphology

The northern populations of *Salamandra algira* spp. are characterised by a smaller total length (maximum length is 210 mm for males and 180 mm for females) compared to *S. algira* ssp. from Chefchauen and Taza (maximum length is 230 mm for males and 226 mm for females). Other differences in lengths were not noted between these populations.

Males of the northern populations develop conspicuous glandular skin protuberances on the whole dorsum and head during mating season. Also the structure of the inner parts of the brachial region of the front legs changes to what externally appears like rounded swollenness or 'nuptial pads'. In other *Salamandra algira* populations that we have studied, only sometimes has a slight development of skin protuberances on the head been observed, however never on the whole dorsum and never in this pronounced way. 'Nuptial pads' were never observed in other populations.

In the northern populations coloration differs from other populations: they lack the vivid black-yellow coloration that is common in other *Salamandra* and the ground colour is dark brown instead of black. There is also a high tendency towards hypoliteism and even melanism. Red coloration is totally absent in these northern specimens whereas *S. algira* ssp. from Taza, Ketama region and Chefchauen have red coloration.

Molecular data

The analyses included 372 bp of cytochrome *b* mitochondrial gene of which 106 were variable and 93 parsimony-informative. The results of the phylogenetic analyses are summarised in fig. 4. ML and MP analyses produced identical topologies. The genus *Salamandra* is monophyletic with two well-supported main clades: the Moroccan clade, which includes *S. algira* ssp. n. and *S. algira* ssp., and the European clade, which includes

Salamandra from the Iberian Peninsula and Switzerland. Within the Moroccan clade, two taxa form two well-supported monophyletic units with no or very low internal variability (0% within *S. algira* ssp. n. (J. Fahies, T. Tagramt) and 0.81% within *S. algira* ssp. (Akshur, Chefchauen)). The genetic variability between the two Moroccan subspecies ranges between 5.9 % and 6.2 %.

Figure 4. Maximum Likelihood (TVM+G; -log likelihood: 1101.99612) phylogenetic tree of *Salamandra* based on mitochondrial cytochrome *b* partial sequences. Numbers adjacent to the nodes indicate, from left to right, the bootstrap support for the ML and MP analysis; e.g. 63/71 =ML/MP.

We therefore conclude that a new subspecies of *Salamandra algira* can be recognised in the Northwest of Morocco as it is different on ecological, morphological and genetic points from other populations found in this country.

***Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n.**

Holotype: Adult female (MNCN 41037) found at 500 m altitude on Jabal Musa (=Jabal Mousa) north Morocco (= terra typica) on 7th December 1997 (see fig. 5). Total length of the holotype is 162.2 mm (see for other measurements Table II). Collected by David Donaire and Francisco Javier Martínez-Medina.

Paratypes: MNCN 41038 is a subadult, MNCN 41039 is a juvenile, ZMFK 77415 is an adult male and ZMA 20011 is an adult male. All four originate from Jabal Musa. MNCN 41040 (fig. 6) is a subadult from 2 km north of Taleta Tagramt (Jabal Bugmil) and MNCN 41041 is a small juvenile from Jabal el Fahies. All animals collected by David Donaire.

Diagnosis: *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. is a relatively slender and smaller subspecies (maximum length 210 mm for males and 180 mm for females). Coloration in general is dull with the background showing shades of seal brown. These animals can always be distinguished from the other subspecies by the reduction of yellow on the tail and the presence of a maximum of four spots on the head (two on the eye-pads and two on the paratoids). In 50% of all animals there are less than four spots. There is a high tendency towards melanism and marked ontogenetic changes in coloration with cleavage and progressive reduction in yellow markings during their lifetime. The yellow can disappear, fade away or turn into a dull shade of grey-white (hypoluteism). Red coloration is absent. There is an optional viviparous reproductive mode. Females produce larvae at advanced developmental stages, with the aquatic stage being frequently skipped.

During mating season, males present conspicuous glandular granules on the skin of the whole dorsum and head. They also have morphological changes in the forearms; it changes to what externally appears like rounded swolleness or 'nuptial pads'.

Figure 5. Holotype (MNCN 41037) of *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n.

Table I. Details of material and sequences used in the present study.

Taxon	Locality	Accession number (Cytb)	Genebank sequence code	Reference
<i>Mertensiella caucasica-1</i>	Sumela, Turkey	AY247736	E17121	this study
<i>Mertensiella caucasica-2</i>	Sumela, Turkey	AY247737	E17122	this study
<i>Salamandra algira tingitana</i> ssp. n.	Jabal El Fahies, Morocco	AY247732	E17127	this study
<i>Salamandra algira tingitana</i> ssp. n.	Tagramt (MCNM 41040), Morocco	AY247733	E300910	this study
<i>Salamandra algira</i> ssp.	Akshur near Talembot, Morocco	AY247734	E17129	this study
<i>Salamandra algira</i> ssp.	Chefchauen, Morocco	AY247735	E171214	this study
<i>Salamandra atra</i>	Switzerland	AAC62313		GARCIA-PARÍS et al., 1998
<i>Salamandra s. longirostris</i>	Grazalema, Spain	AAC62311		GARCIA- PARÍS et al., 1998
<i>Salamandra s. morenica</i>	North of Cordoba, Spain	AAC62310		GARCIA- PARÍS et al., 1998
<i>Salamandra s. crespoides</i>	Foia-Monchique, Portugal	AAC62308		GARCIA- PARÍS et al., 1998

Description of the holotype (see figure 5): Dorsal ground colour is jet black with ten daffodil-yellow spots arrayed in a more or less longitudinal pattern; four spots on the head (one on each eye pad and paratoid), one small one in the neck, four in the dorsum and three connected ones in the sacrum. The spot on the left eye pad is threefold shaped, whereas the spot on the right eye pad is similarly shaped but with a greater reduction in yellow coloration. Four small dots on the right lateral side and none in the left lateral one, of which two are in the trunk and two in the sacral side; the tail is mainly black but with two dots at the base on the left side and one dot at the base of the right side. There is one spot on the left forearm, one at the base of the right arm, one at the base of the left leg and two very small vague ones on the right leg. Ventral side coloration, including tail and throat regions, is dark reddish-brown with no yellow spots.

Figure 6. Paratype MNCN 41040 *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. from Taleta Tagramt.

Derivatio nominis: Tingitana refers to the old Roman province where this form of salamander is found. The geographical meaning of this term is restricted to the surroundings of Tangier around the triangle formed by Tangier, Ceuta and Tetuan that comprises the Tingitanian district as mentioned in BOULENGER (1889) and FAHD (2001).

Variation in coloration: About 30 animals were photographed and partly measured in the field. From photographs we can analyse that 15 animals (50 %) have four spots on the head (paratoids and eye pads), while the other 15 animals (50 %) have fewer or no spots at all on their heads. Thirteen (43.3 %) of these 30 animals, especially juveniles, show blue whitish coloration on the eye pads. Two animals (6.6%) were completely melanistic, whereas 5 (16.6%) showed very strong reduction in the yellow coloration (hypoluteism). Fifteen (50%), mostly adult, animals showed signs of reduction in the yellow pattern and the remaining eight (26.6%) had clear full coloured spots. Red coloration was absent in all of the photographed animals (100%) and all others that were observed. Ground colour within this subspecies varies from completely jet-black to reddish-dark brown. The yellow coloration varied from orange-yellow to daffodil yellow in 10 animals (33.3 %), which had a dark ground colour, whereas it varied from daffodil-yellow to vague whitish-yellow in 13 animals (43.3%) that showed a brownish ground colour. Juveniles, and sometimes adults, can have white-bluish or greenish coloration of the spots above the eyes, instead of yellow.

Dorsal yellow spots array in a single longitudinal or zigzag pattern. They never occur in two rows nor do they form longitudinal lines; however ontogenetic changes can give the illusion of two rows of spots (see fig. 7).

We have observed changes in coloration in animals kept in captivity (BOGAERTS, 2002). Spots tend to be proportionally bigger, more rounded and less numerous in juveniles than in animals that have reached maturity. Therefore the same animal will have fewer spots as a juvenile than as an adult. The yellow spots undergo a progressive reduction in shape and chromatism during the life-span; spots gradually fade or split so that in adulthood they are proportionately smaller, letter shaped (e.g. C, O and Y) and appear more numerous. This reduction usually starts in the centre of the spot and the coloration can gradually change to a dull shade of grey-white (hypoluteism), or disappear entirely.

Table II. Measurements *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. holotype and paratypes.

Locality		Number	Sex/age	1	2	3	4	5
Jabal Musa	Holotype	MNCN 41037	female	162.2	96.8	65.4	23	16.9
Jabal Musa	Paratype	MNCN 41038	subadult	108	64.8	43.2	16.7	11.6
Jabal Musa	Paratype	MNCN 41039	juvenile	82.8	51.6	31.2	14.3	9.6
TaletaTagramt	Paratype	MNCN 41040	subadult	117	70	47	16	13
Jabal el Fahies	Paratype	MNCN 41041	neonate	41	26	15	8	6
Jabal Musa	Paratype	ZMFK 77415	male	173.5	98.5	75	25	17.6
TaletaTagramt	Paratype	ZFMK 77888	subadult	122	70.4	51.6	18.3	13
Jabal Musa	Paratype	ZMA 20011	male	187.4	106.4	81	25.5	18.1

Table II cont.

Locality		Number	Sex/age	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Jabal Musa	Holotype	MNCN 41037	female	26.9	28.5	26.1	27.3	6.5	6.5	6.8	15
Jabal Musa	Paratype	MNCN 41038	subadult	18.2	19.6	19.3	22	5	5.2	5	10.1
Jabal Musa	Paratype	MNCN 41039	juvenile	15.4	15.3	16	16.6	4	4	5.1	6.5
TaletaTagramt	Paratype	MNCN 41040	subadult	20.5	21.6	21	13	6	5	5.5	12.2
Jabal el Fahies	Paratype	MNCN 41041	neonate	7.5	7	7.2	7.1	1.4	1.5	2.5	5.1
Jabal Musa	Paratype	ZMFK 77415	male	29.6	31.3	35.2	30.1	7.2	7	7.6	15.4
TaletaTagramt	Paratype	ZFMK 77888	subadult	21	18.7	23.7	23	4.7	5.2	5.1	11.3
Jabal Musa	Paratype	ZMA 20011	male	34.2	30.2	37.2	41.2	7.6	cut	8	14.7

Body dimensions in mm. MNCN 41040 and 41041 measurements 6 to 13 were done on animals, which were already preserved

1 = total length, 2 = snout-vent length, 3 = tail length, 4 = head length, 5 = head width, 6 = arm length left, 7 = arm length right, 8 = length of hind leg left, 9 = length of hind leg right, 10 = length of 3rd finger left, 11 = length of 3rd finger right, 12 = snout length, 13 = length of lower jaw. Measurements taken as in JOGER & STEINFARTZ (1994).

Figure 7. Male *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. from Jabal Musa (below, smaller animal), compared to male *Salamandra algira* ssp. from Chefchauen (above, larger).

Distribution: *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. is found from near sea level in Ceuta, Spain (DONAIRE-BARROSO & BOGAERTS, 2001) to up to 750 meters in Jabal el Haus (= Sierra del Haus), Morocco (MARTÍNEZ-MEDINA, 2001). MARTÍNEZ-MEDINA (2001) lists seven localities in the Jabal el Haus, two are the same as ours (the first author prospected together with Martínez-Medina) and the others are very close to our own findings. We have found the new form at:

- Ceuta, costal northeastern slope on mainland (alt. 60 m)
- North face of Jabal el Fahies (alt. 200-600 m)
- Central eastern slope of Jabal el Fahies (alt. 400 m)
- Road just south of Jabal Chendir (alt. 350 m)
- North east of Taleta Tagramt on Jabal Bugmil and Hafa el Rauda (alt. 400 – 500 m)
- Cudia Telaya (=Kudiet el Talaya) near Aïn Lahassen

The presence of *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. seems to be restricted to the limestone formations in the mountains or hills north and west of Tetuan, comprising the Moroccan kabilas of Uad Ras, El Has, Anyera and the Spanish hills of the autonomous city of Ceuta (fig. 8).

Figure 8. Detailed distribution of *Salamandra algira* in the Tingitana peninsula and adjacent Rif Mountains.

Black dots: *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. (1-12). Red dots: *Salamandra algira* ssp. (13-16) with red coloration.

1. Jabal Musa
2. Jabal el Fahies
3. Ceuta
4. Jabal el Fahies
5. Boquete de Anyera
6. Road south of Jabal Chendir
7. Jabal Bugmil, 2 km N of Taleta Tagramt
8. Melusa, 4 km north
9. Jabal el Haus (=Jabal el Haouz)
10. Jabal el Haus
11. Hafa el Mensuar
12. Cudia Telaya near Aïn Lahassen
13. South of Bu Semlal, west of Jabal Ajnan (Beni Hosmar)
14. Nakhla dam
15. Near Oulad Didous, Jabal Izmamen (Beni Maharon)
16. Cudia Adru, near Afernu (Beni Arus)
17. Chefchauen (not on the map; it lies 60 km southwards of Tetuan)

Ecological data

Salamandra algira tingitana has been found in a north face coastal pine tree forest at Ceuta, on rocky slopes and in marginal cork forest of Jabal Musa and Jabal el Fahies and in hardly vegetated karst formations just north of Taleta Tagramt (Jabal Bugmil). It is mainly found in rocky hilly areas and although its presence is not strictly restricted to limestone formations, the main core of the population dwells there.

Active salamanders were found from October until March. They were outside their shelters at night when it was raining or in the days just after rain when the soil is wet. In these months, during the daytime these animals could be found by turning over stones. In drier days during autumn, winter and early spring, or outside this period, turning over stones was unsuccessful.

The location near Taleta Tagramt is characterised by barren limestone rocks with even meters deep cracks and crevices (fig. 3). At this locality a pond is found about 50 m away

but we never detected larvae in it. In both Jabal el Fahies locations water points were also available but larvae were never found there either.

Activity outside the shelters was only observed when there was high humidity or rain. In one case, air temperature was 16°C. Adult males were found to be the most active, but subadults and even juveniles of both sexes were frequently active as well. During the daytime animals could only be found under small/medium stones when it had rained recently or was actively raining. They were occasionally found under huge rocks when the soil was drier.

Figure 9. Melanistic male of *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. with glandular skin.

Figure 10. Male *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. from Jabal Musa showing reduction of yellow in the centre of the spots.

DISCUSSION

Coloration

In *S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. an ontogenic reduction in yellow coloration is present. They lack the vivid black-yellow coloration that is common in other *Salamandra* and the ground colour is dark brown instead of black. There is a high tendency towards hypoluteism and even melanism (see figs. 9,10). Red coloration is totally absent whereas *S. algira* from most other areas show red coloration. We suggest the aposematic coloration has undergone changes because of a subterranean way of living (see Ecology), as is visible in the strong reduction of yellow coloration. This coloration was not needed, as there are no predators in these caves.

Five animals found at Cudia Adu (southwest of Tetuan) have strong yellow-black coloration and no signs of reduction of the yellow spots (as observed in populations from Taza and Chefchauen). But they show no sign of red coloration dorsally as in *S. algira tingitana* ssp. n.

Distribution

The distribution of *S. algira tingitana* ssp. n. is clearly marked geographically by natural borders. The Strait of Gibraltar and the Mediterranean sea border it to the north and east (fig. 8). To the west lies the Tangier plain and to the south the valley of the Oued Hajera / Río Martil (Tetuan) which probably has cut off the connection with other *Salamandra* populations in the southern Rif mountains (fig. 11). All localities mentioned in MARTÍNEZ-MEDINA et al. (1997) and MARTÍNEZ-MEDINA (2001) belong to this subspecies (Martínez-Medina, pers. comm.). The area has 800 to 1200 mm of annual rainfall and is marked as humid and perhumid bioclimatic zones (in FAHD, 2001).

Somewhat puzzling are the museum specimens BMNH 1889.3.12.9-16 and SMF 146-147 from “Benider Hills, near Tangier”, all collected by H. Vaucher (depicted in mirror view in BOULENGER (1889) and there called *Salamandra maculosa*). They resemble *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. in shape, size and colour pattern (fig. 12). We propose to allocate them to this new subspecies, although these are juvenile and subadult specimens that do not show the typical reduction in coloration or cleavage of the spots as observed in adult specimens of *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n.

Figure 11. Distribution map of *Salamandra algira* in North Africa with remarks on coloration, and an indication of the distribution of *Salamandra salamandra longirostris* in southern Spain

- in black *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. (melanism and hypoliteism)
- in red *Salamandra algira* spp. (with yellow and red coloration)
- in blue *Salamandra algira* spp. (no data on coloration)
- in yellow (terra typica) *Salamandra algira* (without red coloration)
- in dark grey *Salamandra salamandra longirostris* in southern Spain

Numbers indicate the region and taxa present.

1. Tangitanian district (North Jebala) *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n.
2. Western Rif mountains
3. Central Rif mountains
4. Middle Atlas
5. Beni Snassen
6. Rarh el Maden
7. Blida Atlas
8. Great Kabylia
9. Edough massif (terra typica) *Salamandra algira*

Unfortunately “Benider Hills” is a rather imprecise geographical area. In fact it is a tribal division ('kabila' in Arabic) of a very large area where many hills occur. We have found five animals a few kilometres to the west of the actual Taleta Beni Ider, in Cudia Adu, which produce aquatic larvae, but they do not resemble the Vaucher specimens in coloration pattern nor the *S. algira tingitana* ssp. n. (see under Coloration). If Vaucher collected these animals near Taleta Beni Ider, it would mean that two *Salamandra* morphotypes occur sympatrically which is highly improbable. “Benider Hills” could refer to an area north of Taleta Beni Ider, closer to Tangier (as stated in the original letter sent by Vaucher to the BMNH London “near Tangier”) but there is no locality called ‘Beni Ider’ near Tangier where BONS & GENIEZ (1996) and SCHLEICH et al. (1996) placed this record.

We believe that Vaucher’s specimens were collected in the hilly area west of the Jabal el Haus range, probably near Aïn Lhassen, because in the latter locality we have found

juvenile animals morphologically very similar to the Vaucher ones. They show resemblance to *S. algira tingitana* ssp. n. This locality is within the borders of the above-presented distribution and we therefore think they should be assigned to this new subspecies.

Ecology

The most surprising and fascinating aspect of *S. algira tingitana* ssp. n. is the viviparous mode of reproduction (DONAIRE & BOGAERTS, 2001; DONAIRE BARROSO et al., 2001). Viviparity seems to be the common mode of reproduction for this subspecies (fig. 13). Deposition of larvae in this form seemed to be related to stress factors. A comparison with other viviparous forms of *Salamandra* shows that the mode of viviparity appears similar to *S. s. bernardezi* found in northern Spain as described by THIESMEIER & HAKER (1990). *S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. and *S. salamandra bernardezi* both give birth to several small-bodied young instead of only 1-3 large-bodied young as seen in *Salamandra atra* and *Salamandra lanzai*. All other populations known from Morocco and Algeria are ovoviviparous. Therefore viviparity seems to be a specific trait for this new subspecies. We think this viviparism could be explained if we assume that a drier climatic period selected ancestors of *S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. that were pushed to shelter all year round inside the karstic rock crevices. If a gradual external dryness of the region was strong enough to first dry up any external water point and later any subterranean water course, animals that had the ability to reproduce by retaining larvae *in utero* for longer periods could survive. This is explained by a capability for oviductal retention, which GARCÍA-PARÍS et al. (2003) consider as a basic ancestral trait for the whole genus *Salamandra*. GARCIA-PARIS et al. (2003) showed that some northern populations of *Salamandra salamandra* produce fully metamorphosed young in such a way. They thought only one group of populations achieved such a step. We show that this happened at least one more time, which adds to their findings that this step may be a relatively simple one.

Figure 12. The *Salamandra* collected by Vaucher from 'Benider Hills' near Tangier.

This cavernicol niche acted as a buffer for the harsher external climatic conditions that might have extinguished nearby populations. This extinction would have created a discontinuity in the distribution range of its ancestors thus allowing juveniles and adults to thrive but because of the permeable property of the limestone, water might have soon

become unavailable or only available for a very short period of time; at this critical point the animals that could produce fully metamorphosed young survived (fig. 13). Locations at Jabal el Fahies and Jabal Musa have a striking resemblance with habitats of *Mertensiella (Salamandra) luschani* in southern Turkey. This species is also live-bearing and deals with the same hostile climatic conditions as *S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. This species is also almost completely restricted to karstic limestone formations (VEITH et al., 2001; S. Bogaerts, pers.

Figure 13. Neonate *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n.

obs.). In *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. the viviparism seems to be genetically fixed, as captive specimens still produce completely developed young even if suitable breeding water is always available. However, this viviparism should not be regarded as entirely fixed, as larvae sometimes are delivered under stress conditions. One aquatic larva was collected in a small pond at Jabal Musa (MARTÍNEZ-MEDINA, 2001) that might have recently been deposited (as the rainy season had just started). It showed signs of metamorphosis one week later. We also found some aquatic larvae near Aïn Lahassen, but further research is necessary on this locality to find about the reproductive mode of this population.

The karstic limestone systems seem very important for long-term survival of this subspecies, but are also probably very important for the species *S. algira* in general. The survival of periods of drought (summer) is possible if animals can hide deep into the ground. These systems of cracks and crevices in the limestone are ideal conditions. It is an extreme illustration of what the needs for this subspecies are: holes and caves going deep in the ground where they can hide from the heat in summer. As they do not need water for reproduction, they have become independent from breeding waters.

Figure 14. Comparison between *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp.n. from Jabal Musa (smaller specimen) and female *Salamandra salamandra longirostris* from Los Barrios, Spain.

Figure 15. Close-up of glandular skin protuberances of a male *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp.n. during the breeding season.

Morphology

S. algira tingitana ssp. n. is clearly smaller in size than other known *S. algira* populations. Measurements on *S. algira*, however, are scarce and very old (see BEDRIAGA, 1883; BOULENGER, 1891; DOUMERGUE, 1901). There is therefore the need to re-measure these animals and to collect new data. For instance, BOULENGER (1891) included the cloaca in the measurements of the tail without mentioning it, hence introducing error when the literature data is used. Maximum total length according to SCHLEICH et al. (1996) is 208 mm (Taza Region); SALVADOR (1996) mentions 226 mm of length, but does not state the locality. We have measured four live adults from Taza and the largest measured 219 mm. Our data shows that *S. algira* ssp. 'Chefchauen' can grow up to 240 mm. *S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. measures a maximum 210 mm in T. Tagramt; 185 mm in Jabal Musa (fig. 14); 180 mm in Jabal el Fahies. Lengths of animals published by MARTÍNEZ-MEDINA et al. (1997) are all smaller.

The observations on a nuptial dress (fig. 15) for *S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. need further research. Comparisons with literature and our own field observations on other *Salamandra* taxa showed nothing comparable; although male *Mertensiella luschani* show strong changes in their skin structure on their dorsal region during the breeding season (S. Bogaerts, pers. obs.).

Molecular analyses

The genetic variability between the two Moroccan subspecies (*S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. and *S. algira* ssp.) ranges between 5.9 % and 6.2 %, and therefore it is higher than the genetic divergence between all the other representatives of the *S. salamandra* group included in this study (*S. s. crespoi*, *S. s. morenica* and the very distinct (fig. 14) *S. s. longirostris*; see Table III). When other described subspecies of the genus *Salamandra* are compared (*S. atra atra* vs. *S. atra aurorae* and all the other subspecies of the *S. salamandra* group), the two Moroccan salamanders, *S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. and *S. algira* ssp. still show the highest genetic divergence of all the comparisons at the subspecies level (S. Carranza, pers. comm.). Overall, the genetic results clearly indicate that the two morphologically distinct *S. a. tingitana* ssp. n. and *S. algira* ssp. also clearly differ at the genetic level.

Table III. Kimura 2-parameters genetic distances between all the specimens used in this study

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1 <i>S. a. tingitana</i> (J. Fahies)	-									
2 <i>S. a. tingitana</i> (Tagramt)	0.00000	-								
3 <i>S. a. algira</i> (Akshur)	0.06219	0.06219	-							
4 <i>S. a. algira</i> (Chefchauen)	0.05931	0.05931	0.00811	-						
5 <i>S. atra</i>	0.11243	0.11243	0.11829	0.11192	-					
6 <i>S. s. crespoi</i>	0.10637	0.10637	0.11939	0.11970	0.07727	-				
7 <i>S. s. longirostris</i>	0.10967	0.10967	0.11604	0.11299	0.06810	0.05359	-			
8 <i>S. s. morenica</i>	0.10336	0.10336	0.11634	0.11665	0.07435	0.01913	0.05075	-		
9 <i>M. caucasica</i> -1	0.21623	0.21623	0.21185	0.21922	0.24233	0.21327	0.23631	0.22468	-	
10 <i>M. caucasica</i> -2	0.21623	0.21623	0.21185	0.21922	0.24233	0.21327	0.23631	0.22468	0.00000	-

STEINFARTZ et al. (2000) found 4.8% of genetic differentiation between *S. algira* from "terra typica" Jabal Edough (=Annaba), Algeria and Chefchauen, Morocco, this divergence is higher than that found for *S. salamandra* and *S. atra*, that indicates that we might even have two species of *Salamandra* in North Africa: an east Algerian form, *S. algira* and a Moroccan form *Salamandra* sp.

Concluding remarks

Future research on other Moroccan and especially Algerian populations can hopefully help to resolve the relationships between the fragmented North African *Salamandra* populations.

Compared with Algerian *S. algira* specimens and animals from other localities in Morocco, *S. algira tingitana* ssp. n. is a form, which can easily be distinguished on the basis of morphology, genetics, distribution, viviparism and sexual dimorphism during the breeding season.

Figure 16. Adult male *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. with aberrant coloration from Jabal Bugmil.

SUMMARY

We describe a new subspecies of *Salamandra algira* in the northwest of Morocco. *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. is a relatively slender and smaller subspecies compared to other *S. algira* populations. It is characterised by smaller total length (maximum length is 210 mm for males and 180 mm for females) compared to *S. algira* ssp. from Chefchauen and Taza (maximum length is 230 mm for males and 226 mm for females). Coloration is, in general, dull-coloured compared to other *S. algira* studied. Red coloration is absent and there is a tendency towards progressive reduction in yellow markings during their lifetime and towards melanism. Yellow markings can disappear, fade away or turn into a dull shade of grey-white. Melanism is present. This new form also shows an optional viviparous reproductive mode. Males during mating season show a nuptial dress with conspicuous glandular skin protuberances on the whole dorsum and head; they also develop morphological changes in the forearms; the skin on the biceps appears like rounded swollenness or 'nuptial pads'.

Resumen

Describimos una nueva subespecie de *Salamandra algira* en el noroeste de Marruecos. *Salamandra algira tingitana* ssp. n. es una forma relativamente menos esbelta y alargada en comparación con el resto de poblaciones de *S. algira*. Se caracteriza por una longitud total menor (longitud máxima de 210 mm para machos y 180 mm para hembras) en comparación con *S. algira* ssp. de Chefchauen y Taza (longitud máxima de 230 mm en machos y 226 mm en hembras). La coloración en comparación con otras formas estudiadas es en general apagada, no existe coloración roja y hay una gran tendencia hacia una reducción progresiva de las manchas amarillas durante la vida. Las manchas amarillas pueden desaparecer, borrarse o convertirse en un tono apagado grisáceo (hipoluteismo). Además existe melanismo. Esta nueva forma también muestra un modo de reproducción diferente, pues existe un modo reproductivo vivíparo opcional y los machos durante la época de celo presentan librea nupcial con llamativas protuberancias glandulares en el dorso y cabeza (gránulos); a la vez que desarrollan cambios

morfológicos en los antebrazos donde la piel de los bíceps parece como redondeada e hinchada formando almohadillas nupciales.

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